

Cruising Chicago's Club Scene with the Yakster **by Brian Paul Kaess**

Back in the time period 1992-1996 in Chicago, I worked at Edgewater Medical Center as an Emergency Room Registration Clerk, and on occasion, would frequent nightclubs on Chicago's north side with a group of co-workers from my job at the E.R.: These included nurses Terri 'Yakster' Yak, Marci, & Jackie Duffy, and others such as her roommate Brandy (from Deerfield), and workers Schroeder, Marie, her sister, and more. Terri was an LPN and Brandy's roommate. She was nicknamed 'the Yakster' by Dr. Thomas, as she was known to have her way in the E.R., especially when talking back to unruly patients. She would say things like: 'I'd rather eat broken glass!' She even once kicked a patient handcuffed on the ground, who was being held by Chicago Police, the Police seemingly oblivious to her actions. Our 'workhorse' doctors included Dr. Thomas, Dr. Snee, Dr. Press, Dr. Park, and more. Dr. Thomas was a skilled ER Doctor and was known to 'bring heart patients back up' who were on the brink of death. No easy task! Thomas would say things like, 'that was most efficacious' and Dr. Press would criticize now and then by saying that's 'bad form'. They always seemed to have the patients best interests at heart.

Marci, who was Jewish, besides being an LPN, was studying for a degree in English and enjoyed 'heading out' to the clubs. Steve Hammer, an RN, who we also worked with, was a Captain in the U.S. Army Reserve and met his Phillipina wife through nursing. Julie was from the Phillipines and a skilled nurse. And there was also Barb from Poland, another RN, and Ben McConnel, a former SSGT in the U.S. Marine Reserves, who seemed to handle the nursing grind quite well. Included was Brock, a nurse who had worked at Cook County Hospital E.R. for twenty years and 'knew the ropes.' He was a proud father of a daughter at U of I. His advice was 'throw out the drugs!' His mantra was 'fuck 'em!'

Some girls I dated were Vicki Valencia (a unit secretary & fellow Lane grad), Melissa (a CNA who lived in the Depaul area), & Kathy (a nurse from the floors on 4 West). Vicki and I went to the Art Institute of Chicago, Melissa and I went to *the Cro-Bar* nightclub and shopping at *Marshall Fields*, and Kathy and I just mingled in her car.

In any case, Terri, who was known to date Dr. Thomas, invited me to visit some nightclubs when we were off-duty from Edgewater and I dutifully agreed. These included *the Smart Bar*, music concerts at the *Cabaret Metro & the Heartland Café*, *the Abbey Pub* and more. We even saw *the Drovers* in concert. Marci, Brandy, and my girlfriend Azra came along for some of these. She almost match-made me with Brandy but I couldn't pull it off. *The Heartland Café* had all kinds of 'pinko' paraphernalia and t-shirts that suggested one should 'Bow to Mao!' We even spent time drinking beers at Jackie Duffy's house with her, her CPD husband (a Navy Vietnam Vet), and Dr. Thomas. This was like an 'old-timers' gathering.

We worked often with CFD (both Paramedics and Fire) and Chicago Police from the 20th/24th District. Two 'workhouse' paramedics who stood out were Mike (Irish-looking) and Jake (?) (tall Hispanic) from CFD 13. They were like hand-and-glove with the ER docs and nurses. A CPD officer named Tom noticed me reading my Philosophy books and gifted me a brand new copy of Albert Camus's unpublished novel *The First Man or Le Premier homme* (1994). I thought it was a nice gesture from a Loyola man who had also studied Philosophy.

Jackie would like saying things, 'Isn't that special?' in a cute sort of way, but she was a skilled nurse and excellent at bandages and caring for pregnant women in labor. She had a nursing 'hubris' towards certain foreign doctors and would say things like: 'Don't let him touch you!'

There was one occasion when an older black teenager and his pregnant white woman came roaring into the the E.R. entrance in their vehicle, barely stopping in time, and leaving their wheels steaming in their wake. He and the girl walked directly to the E.R. treatment area, without stopping to register, and Brock, sensing his disdain for the rules, told him bluntly, 'No, brother, you ain't comin' down here!' He did not oblige Brock and tried to force his way through three people (including myself) to be with his woman. We gently tackled him and later I even gave him a cup of coffee as he came to his senses. The woman, yeah, she turned out to be ok, and was treated accordingly.

I had worked the E.R. for awhile but there are some events that 'stuck out.' Three of these incidents, I nicknamed 'Sex, Drugs, and Rock n' Roll.' The first (i.e. Sex) involved a waiter named Nick who I knew slightly because he worked at *Kopi Café* in Andersonville where I would buy coffee and so on. He came in and told me, 'I met this girl and we had sex, and it turned out she had AIDS and she didn't tell me, and now I have AIDS!' It seemed pretty tragic because he gave me the impression he had just unknowingly received a 'death sentence', a young man in his prime!

The next case (i.e. Drugs) was a girl named Jennifer Flaherty, a young Irish-looking 19 year old. She had been wheeled in DOA by the police and when they showed her I.D., I was shocked because she looked so young! The story went that she and her young female friend had been at a Reggae Bar and two black men approached them and offered them drinks and when the pair accepted, they didn't realize that the two men had spiked their drinks. Thus, when she drank, it resulted in her death.

The last case (i.e. Rock n' Roll) was a young man who came in as a trauma patient. Someone had struck him over the back, head and arms with a wooden object or guitar or something and when it impacted, the object splintered and pierced his body with all sort of wooden shavings. He came in a bit of a mess, at least from all the wooden shavings.

That pretty much sums up my 'clubbing' experience with members from Edgewater's E.R. community as well as the last few tales of certain unfortunate patients who arrived for quality care. I can honestly say, no matter how busy it got, the staff took the welfare of the patients with the utmost seriousness.

So no wonder, when we wanted to 'blow off a little steam' or 'party on the martyr!' we would head out with a certain vengeance and zeal to go clubbing amidst the glitter that *was and is* Chicago's nightlife.